

The Gibbs Paradox and Its Relation To Work

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The Gibbs paradox is often described in terms of Shannon's entropy and microscopic statistical mechanics. Here we try to understand the situation by only using the first law of thermodynamics $dE = TdS - PdV$ with P given by the ideal gas law: $PV=NkT$ and $E=3/2Nkt$. We find that one may derive the Sackur-Tetrode entropy equation strictly from considerations of $E=3/2 kT$ so that $dE=0$ $dT=0$ yields a V dependent piece of dS and $V=\text{constant}$, a T dependent piece of dS (hence S). There remains a $g(N)$ piece which may be fixed in the following manner. If one wishes to have $S_1+S_2=S$ where $S_1=S_2=$ entropy in half the box (i.e. the box is partitioned into two equal parts), then the form $TdS = T dS_1 + TdS_2$ ((1)). If one considers T constant and V changing, then P is the same in partition 1, partition 2 and the whole case. This means that writing $P_1 dV$, $P_2 dV$ and $P_{\text{total}} dV$ are all the same expression, but ((1)) for T constant, V changing uses a sum and so for the case of T constant, V changing, one cannot simply have an $N \ln V$ term, but must consider a $g(N)$ terms such that $2N \ln(V) + 2g(N) = 2N \ln(2V) + g(2N)$. This then leads to $g(N) = N \ln(N)$ (which in the Stirling approximation is $\ln(N!)$), but we argue that this term arises because of the ideal gas law and $S_1+S_2=S$ considerations without any a priori consideration of identical particles (which is the usual argument presented to justify $N \ln(N)$). We note, however, that mathematically $N \ln(N)$ is $\ln(N!)$ in the large N limit and so it is not surprising that an identical particle argument may arise, but it need not if one only considers the ideal gas law results $E=3/2 NkT$, $PV= Nkt$ and $dE=TdS - PdV$. We note that the Ideal case law was determined experimentally and that $E=3/2NKT$ may probably be used without a microscopic derivation.

Gibbs Paradox and Identical Particles

Thermodynamic entropy, although being a state variable, must satisfy the First Law of Thermodynamics:

$$dE = TdS - PdV \quad ((1))$$

For an ideal gas:

$$E=3/2 Nkt \quad ((2a)) \quad \text{and} \quad PV=NkT \quad ((2b))$$

((2a)) and ((2b)) may be thought of as experimental results, we argue.

Traditionally, Shannon's entropy - $\sum_i p(e_i) \ln(p(e_i))$ is introduced into Maxwell-Boltzmann microscopic statistical mechanics with:

$$p(e_i) = \exp(-e_i/T) / \sum_i \exp(-e_i/T) \quad ((3))$$

((3)), however, leads to an expression for Shannon's entropy which does not allow for:

$$S = S_1 + S_2 \quad ((4))$$

where $S_1 = S_2$ represent the entropies in each half of a box with a partition creating two equal compartments (same N, T, V) while S represents the entire box. The problem, called the Gibb's Paradox, is resolved by using:

$$\text{Normalization} = 1/Z \text{ where } Z = 1/N! \sum \text{over } i \exp(-e_i/T) \quad ((5))$$

$N!$ is said to account for the indistinguishability of N particles. We note that the Maxwell-Boltzmann result $\exp(-e_i/T)$ only holds for large N and so one may automatically assume:

$$\ln(N!) = N \ln(N) \quad ((6)) \text{ Stirling's approximation}$$

We note, however, that technically Stirling's approximation contains other N terms and so technically one does not have $S_1 + S_2 = S$ if one includes these extra terms i.e.

$$\ln(N!) = N \ln(N) - N + 0.5 \ln(N) \quad ((6)) \text{ in the DeMoivre Form}$$

We also note that $\exp(-e_i/T)$, which may be derived by reaction balance only matches the maximization of

$$\ln(N!) / \text{Product over } i n(e_i)! \text{ subject to } \sum \text{over } i e_i n(e_i) = E_{\text{total}} \quad ((7))$$

If one uses $\ln(n!) = n \ln(n)$ and does not include higher n terms. Reaction balance, however, automatically yields $\exp(-e_i/T)$ through $p(e_i)p(e_j) = p(e_i + e_j)$ and one does not have to worry about Stirling's approximation and how many terms to retain. We note the $\exp(-e_i/T)$ is also an approximate solution based on a large N and thus argue that the form ((6)) is the one consistent with reaction balance. If one were to start (a priori) with ((7)), it is not clear why one would necessarily use ((6)) and not include further terms, but perhaps the argument is that for N very large, only the largest term is necessary. Certainly in ideal gases one has a very large value of N .

The Gibbs Paradox and the Notion of Work

We try to resolve the Gibb's Paradox without making use of any notion of indistinguishability of particles. In particular, we only use the First Law of Thermodynamics and the two ideal gas equations ((2a)) and ((2b)). We argue that if one insists on:

$$S_1 + S_2 = S \quad ((8))$$

where $S_1=S_2$ for each equal compartment of a total volume $2V$ linked to S , then one must also consider the interaction related term TdS which appears in the First Law of Thermodynamics.

Using ((8)), one has:

$$TdS_1 + TdS_2 = T dS \quad ((9))$$

$$\text{Now for } T \text{ constant: } dE=0 = TdS - PdV \quad ((10))$$

P is the same in each compartment and in the total volume because $PV=NkT$. In each compartment one has half the particles, but also half the volume, so P is unchanged. One may readily see that ((9)) leads to a problem if one uses the same dV because:

$$TdS_1 = TdS_2 = PdV \quad \text{and} \quad TdS = PdV \quad ((11a))$$

((11)) seems to contradict ((8)). One may note that changing the entire gas volume by dV is not the same as changing each compartment by dV . Each compartment would need to be changed by $dV/2$. Thus:

$$\text{For } S_1 = 2T dS(N/2, V/2)/d(V/2) (dV/2) = P(V,N) dV \quad \text{and} \quad T dS(N,V) = P(V,N) dV \quad ((11b))$$

$$((11b)), \text{ however, is mathematically the same as: } 2T dS(N/2, V/2)/dV dV = P(V,N) dV \quad ((11c))$$

If one uses the fact that S may contain a term of $g(N)$ (and in fact must contain such a term if $S_1+S_2=S$ based on ((11b))), where g is unknown, then, one may use, for T constant:

$$T dS/dV dV = NkT/V dV \quad \text{or} \quad S \text{ behaves as } N \ln(V) + g(N) \quad ((12))$$

$$\text{Using ((8)): } 2g(N) + 2N \ln(V) = g(2N) + 2N \ln(2V) \quad \text{or} \quad g(2N) - 2g(N) = 2N \ln(2)$$

$$\text{A solution is: } g(N) = -N \ln(N) \quad ((13))$$

In other words, if one is only interested in TdS (for N constant) then only T and/or V may change and $g(N)$ is not really an issue, but if one considers S as a state variable by itself, then $g(N)$ must be known and accounted for. It is the V dependent portion of S , linked to $-PdV$, which causes the imbalance in S_1+S_2 versus S , if one does not include $g(N)$. This follows from the asymmetrical functional form of N and V in $N \ln(V)$.

One may note that if N is large, which it is, that $N \ln(N) \approx \ln(N!)$, but no notion of particle indistinguishability has been used.

To find the T dependence of entropy, one may set V constant and use:

$$3/2 N kT = T dS/dT \quad ((14))$$

This yields a term: $S_{\text{piece}} = \frac{3}{2} N \ln(T)$ ((15))

Thus, the full expression for entropy should be:

$$\frac{3}{2} N \ln(T) + \text{constant}(\text{no } N, T, V) - N \ln(N) + N \ln(V) \text{ ((16))}$$

((16)) matches the Sackur-Tetrode equation (2).

Thus, we argue that one is not forced to consider the indistinguishability of particles (or any quantum notions because indistinguishability is often attributed to quantum features), but may obtain the $N \ln(N)$ term in S directly from considerations of work (ideal gas law for P) together with $S=S_1+S_2$, for $S_1=S_2$ representing two equal compartments, and S , the entire box of ideal gas.

Conclusion

A problem, called the Gibb's Paradox, arises if one uses microscopic Maxwell-Boltzmann statistical mechanics to describe an ideal gas. In such a case, one may write: $p(e_i) = \exp(-e_i/T) / Z$, where $1/Z$ is the usual normalization constant. If one uses Shannon's entropy $-\sum_i p(e_i) \ln(p(e_i))$, then $S_1+S_2 \neq S$ if $S_1=S_2$ represent two equal compartments of an ideal gas and S , the entire box of gas. The remedy is to replace Z with $1/N! Z$ and argue that $N!$ accounts for the indistinguishability of particles. This is further attributed to quantum mechanics.

Here, we consider only the first law of Thermodynamics $dE = TdS - PdV$ with $E = \frac{3}{2} NkT$ and $PV = NkT$. We note that the requirement $S_1+S_2=S$ must be compatible with $dS_1+dS_2 = dS$ for T constant and V changing. In such a case, P is the same in compartment 1, compartment 2 and the whole case. If one considers the volume form of S , for $T=\text{constant}$ and $dE=0$, then $T dS(\text{volume}) - NkT/V dV=0$. This implies that: $S(\text{volume}) = N \ln(V) + g(N) + f(N, T) + \text{constant}(\text{no } V, T, N)$, where g and f are unknown. One may see that $N \ln(V)$ does not allow for $S_1+S_2=S$ unless $g(N) = -N \ln(N)$. To find $f(N, T)$, one may hold V constant and use $dE = \frac{3}{2} N dT = T df/dT$ so $f = \frac{3}{2} N \ln(T)$. As a result, the full entropy should be: $S = \text{constant}(\text{no } V, T, N) - N \ln(N) + N \ln(V) + \frac{3}{2} N \ln(T)$, which is the Sackur-Tetrode result. Even though $N \ln(N) = \ln(N!)$, via Stirling's equation, there is no a priori reason one is forced to consider indistinguishability of particles, it seems. We show here that work related considerations together with $S_1+S_2 = S$ are enough.

References

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2. https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Sackur%E2%80%93Tetrode_equation